

MECHANICAL BEHAVIORS OF THREE-DIMENSIONAL HIERARCHICAL LATTICE TRUSS STRUCTURES

Jian Xiong¹, Qianqian Wu¹, Ying Gao¹, Xingyu Wei¹

¹Center for Composite Materials and Structures, Harbin Institute of Technology, Harbin, China

Email: xiongjian0309@126.com, web page: <http://homepage.hit.edu.cn/pages/jianxiong>

Abstract

Mechanical properties and failure mechanisms of “corrugated-pyramidal” hierarchical lattice truss structures were investigated through analytical modelling and detailed numerical simulations. To this end, the performance of the structures under small deformations was investigated based on continuous displacements and equilibrium formulations. Every possible collapse mode of the second order truss structures were predicted under out of plane compression and shear. Theoretical closed-form expressions for strength at each collapse mode were derived and employed to construct collapse mechanism maps. These maps can further be used to demonstrate the relations between collapse modes and of the structures. Our results show that for low relative densities, second order trusses demonstrate significantly higher compressive and shear collapse strength compared to their first order counterparts with same mass. The work provides insight into the role of structural hierarchy in tuning the mechanical behaviour of sandwich structures, and new opportunities for designing ultra-lightweight lattice truss structures with optimal performance.

Keywords: Lattice truss; Hierarchical structure; Sandwich structure; Mechanical properties; Failure mechanism map.

1. Introduction

Lakes [1] is among the pioneers in proposing the idea of structural hierarchy in natural and man-made materials. These so-called “fractal-appearing” structures have been shown to possess enhanced physical properties such as improved strength and toughness. Even at nanoscales, it has been shown that carbon nanotube ropes with hierarchical helical structures exhibit superior mechanical properties such as larger failure strain, easily tunable elastic properties, and higher energy storage ability compared to bundles of straight nanotubes [2]. Taking wood [3] and bone [4] as biological materials with hierarchical architecture, their internal microstructure is composed of tiny truss-like elements contributing to their enhanced energy absorption and anti-vibration characteristics. Therefore, integrating the concept of structural hierarchy with man-made lattice structures will potentially improve the ability of

truss elements to resist buckling, thereby reaching the maximum load-carrying capacity of the system. To this end, for the first time, we propose the concept of “corrugated-pyramidal” hierarchical lattice truss structures, which are designed based on pyramidal lattice sandwich structures introduced earlier. Closed-form expressions for strength at different collapse modes are derived and employed to construct collapse mechanism maps, which can further be used to reveal the failure mechanism of our hierarchical sandwich structures.

2. Topology of hierarchical lattice truss structures

We propose the concept of “corrugated-pyramidal” hierarchical lattice truss structures, which are designed based on pyramidal lattice sandwich structures, as shown in Figure 1. Closed-form expressions for strength at different collapse modes are derived and employed to construct collapse mechanism maps, which can further be used to reveal the failure mechanism of our hierarchical sandwich structures. Finally, the effects of structural hierarchy are highlighted by comparing the results with those of non-hierarchical counterparts.

Figure 1 Unit cell of “corrugated-pyramidal” hierarchical lattice truss structures

Results and discussion

All the results have been summarized in Figures 2-5. Our results show that second order trusses are less efficient than first order pyramidal structures of same mass in terms of compressive and shear stiffness. However, for low relative densities, second order trusses demonstrate significantly higher compressive and shear collapse strength compared to their first order counterparts with same mass.

Figure 2 Comparisons of compressive stiffness between hierarchical and first order pyramidal truss structures with different relative densities.

Figure 3 Comparisons of compressive strength between hierarchical and first order pyramidal truss structures with different relative densities.

Figure 4 Comparisons of shear stiffness between hierarchical and first order pyramidal truss structures with different relative densities.

Figure 5 Comparisons of the in-plane shear strength between hierarchical and first order pyramidal truss structures with different relative densities.

Conclusions

In the present paper, the static characteristic of the “corrugated-pyramidal” hierarchical lattice truss structure has been carefully discussed. Analytical expressions of different failure modes have been derived under out-of-plane compression and shear. The relevant finite element simulations are conducted to verify the validity of the analytical solution, and good correlations between analytical predictions and finite element simulations are achieved. The collapse mechanism maps are constructed based on the analytical expressions for the out-of-plane compressive and shear in each of these modes in order to investigate the influence of the geometric dimensions of structural hierarchy on different kinds of failure modes.

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